

Features of the Dynamics of a Nanoparticle Motion Under the Action of the Light Pressure Force of an Evanescent Wave in the Linear Approximation

A. Ch. Svistun,* E. V. Musafirov, and L. S. Gaida

Yanka Kupala State University of Grodno, 22 Ozeshko Str, Grodno 230023, BELARUS

D. V. Guzatov

Yanka Kupala State University of Grodno, 22 Ozeshko Street, Grodno 230023, BELARUS

The action of light pressure forces of an evanescent electromagnetic wave, formed by total internal reflection at the dielectric-liquid interface, on dielectric spherical nanoparticles located in a liquid medium is considered. An analytical solution for the equation of motion of a nanoparticle under the action of the scattering force of an evanescent wave, taking into account the drag force of the medium in the approximation of small displacements, is obtained. It is shown that the applicability region of linearization does not strongly depend on the sign of the discriminant of the characteristic equation of the linearized system, but rather on the initial conditions and observation time.

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1. Introduction

Optical manipulation of micro- and nano-objects is one of the most dynamically developing areas of modern photonics. Since the first experiments by Arthur Ashkin on acceleration and trapping of particles by radiation pressure [1], methods of optical control of particle position have found wide application in physics, biology, and materials science [2–5]. Of particular interest is the use of evanescent (inhomogeneous, surface) electromagnetic waves, which arise near the interface of media under conditions of total internal reflection or in waveguide structures [6–9].

Evanescent waves possess unique properties: their amplitude decays exponentially with distance from the surface, they are characterized by a specific structure of momentum and angular momentum, including the so-called “transverse

spin”. These features open new possibilities for controlling nanoparticles that are inaccessible when using ordinary bulk waves. The relevance of the topic is confirmed by the appearance of a number of fundamental and applied works, including recent studies on optical levitation and manipulation of particles in the near field of integrated optical structures [10–18].

The study of optical deposition of nanoparticles in dense nanosuspensions, conducted in [19], focuses on the analysis of concentration profiles formed under laser radiation. This method allows effective study of particle behavior, their interaction and distribution in high-density media, which is critical for creating new materials.

The method of stable holding of a nanoparticle inside a photonic jet stream, additionally modulated by a standing wave from reflection off a dielectric surface, is described in [20]. This approach creates highly localized, subwavelength traps with high energy

*E-mail: svistun_ach@grsu.by

density in microfluidic channels, enabling efficient manipulation of particles with low power consumption due to the balance of light pressure of laser radiation and liquid viscosity.

In [21] it is shown that radiation pressure of an evanescent field induces forces in the piconewton range acting on microparticles near interfaces, causing accelerated parallel motion and capture by a vertical gradient force (the scattering force directs particles parallel to the interface, while the gradient force pushes them toward it). Measurements often use total internal reflection to track particle velocity, which depends on laser power and increases with approach to the surface perpendicular to it, often limited by the Debye length.

In [22] a method for creating active motion of colloidal structures without using a chemical medium is investigated. It is shown that light field gradients induce thermo-osmotic forces acting on nearby passive particles, providing asymmetric (non-reciprocal) interactions. Interaction between active and passive colloids leads to formation of various structures (dimers, trimers, quadromers) and emergence of complex motion types, such as active translational motion and chiral (rotational) motion.

Results of calculations of nanoparticle concentration changes in water under continuous laser irradiation are presented in [23]. It is shown that larger particles settle to the cuvette bottom faster than small nanoparticles in a dispersed medium, affecting the particle size distribution function.

The dynamics of nanoparticles in an evanescent wave field is a complex process balancing between optical forces and medium resistance. A key feature is that the nature of particle motion (whether it will be trapped, repelled, or pass without stopping) is determined not only by laser radiation parameters, but also by properties of the particle itself and the surrounding liquid. Analysis of this motion usually reduces to constructing phase portraits that clearly show all possible trajectories and

system states [24, 25]. These works show that depending on system parameters (laser beam power and angle of incidence, particle size and material), various motion scenarios can be realized on the phase plane:

1. *No-capture regime* (no singular points). In this regime, the gradient force cannot fully compensate other factors. Particle localization does not occur, the trajectory crosses the field region. The system phase portrait is characterized by absence of fixed points.
2. *Stable localization regime* (stable node or focus). This regime corresponds to operation of an optical trap ensuring asymptotic stability of equilibrium. A particle in an evanescent wave field tends to an equilibrium point characterized by a fixed coordinate and zero velocity. On the phase portrait this appears as a stable node (monotonic, aperiodic approach) or a stable focus (approach to equilibrium via damped oscillations).
3. *Unstable equilibrium regime* (saddle). A saddle point corresponds to an unstable equilibrium position. System presence at this point is possible only in an idealized case of no perturbations. Under real conditions, any small perturbation (e.g., Brownian motion) drives the system from equilibrium, causing it to evolve along unstable directions. On the phase portrait this appears as a saddle point with incoming and outgoing separatrices.

Modern research allows not only trapping a particle, but also controlling its position in space. For particles made of materials with high refractive index (e.g., silicon), Mie resonances are characteristic. At certain wavelengths, particle-field interaction sharply intensifies, leading to giant growth of light pressure forces. This enables efficient manipulation of particles even at modest radiation power [26].

One key problem of near-field manipulation is strong particle attraction to the surface, risking adhesion (sticking) and increasing viscous friction. A solution may be using two laser beams with different wavelengths [6]. One wave has large penetration depth and attracts the particle, while the other has small depth and repels it, creating a “potential well” at some distance from the surface. For example, for a silicon sphere of 130 nm diameter irradiated by lasers with wavelengths 532 nm and 638 nm (total power 100 mW), it is possible to stably hold the particle at a distance of 60 to 100 nm from the surface, significantly reducing adhesion risk. Dynamics strongly depends on surrounding liquid viscosity. In water, drag force is significant and quickly damps particle velocity, making stable capture more likely than, e.g., in air.

These effects are valid for a narrow size range. For particles with diameter more than ~200–300 nm, other effects begin to matter, while for smaller particles, Brownian motion becomes increasingly significant, which can “knock” the particle out of the optical trap [6, 27]. Research shows that, e.g., carbon nanoparticles smaller than 200 nm in upper atmospheric layers can heat to luminescence temperatures, which also changes their dynamics [28].

Thus, nanoparticle motion dynamics in an evanescent field is a result of fine tuning of many parameters, opening wide possibilities for precision matter control at the nanoscale.

The present work is devoted to further development of theoretical concepts on the mechanism of light pressure action of an evanescent field arising under total internal reflection conditions on dielectric nanoparticles in a liquid medium.

2. Dynamics of nanoparticle motion

Consider the equation of motion of a nanoparticle in the field of an evanescent wave under the action of the scattering force. It should

be noted that in an evanescent wave the scattering force depends exponentially on the coordinate z (the x axis is directed perpendicular to the interface, and the z axis is directed parallel) and has the form [24, 25]:

$$F^{\text{scat}} = F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z),$$

where

$$F_0^{\text{scat}} = \frac{8\pi n_s n_m^4 k_0^4 \alpha_p^2}{3c} f_p I_0^{\text{trans}} \sin \theta,$$

n_s is the refractive index of the dielectric; n_m is the refractive index of the liquid; $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number in vacuum, where λ is the wavelength; c is the speed of light in vacuum; $\alpha_p = a^3(n_p^2 - n_m^2)/(n_p^2 + 2n_m^2)$ is the polarizability of a nanoparticle of radius a located in a liquid; n_p is the refractive index of the nanoparticle material;

$$f_p = \frac{3[2k_0 a \chi \cosh(2k_0 a \chi) - \sinh(2k_0 a \chi)]}{(2k_0 a \chi)^3}$$

is a correction factor due to integration over the nanoparticle volume, which tends to unity in the case $2k_0 a \chi \ll 1$; $\chi = \sqrt{n_s^2 \sin^2 \theta - n_m^2}$; θ is the angle that the direction of wave propagation makes with the x axis; $I_0^{\text{trans}} = (cn_m/8\pi)|A_0|^2$ is the amplitude value of intensity; $A_0 = 2E_0 n_s \cos \theta / (n_s \cos \theta + \varphi)$ is the amplitude of medium oscillation; $\varphi = \sqrt{n_m^2 - n_s^2 \sin^2 \theta}$; E_0 is the wave amplitude; $\beta = 2k_0 \chi$.

Then the equation for the motion of a nanoparticle in the field of an evanescent wave along the direction of its propagation (along the z axis), taking into account the drag force on the nanoparticle motion in the liquid (Stokes force), will be (taking into account that the nanoparticle is raised above the interface):

$$m_p \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = -\gamma \frac{dz}{dt} + F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z) \quad (1)$$

or

$$m_p \ddot{z} = -\gamma \dot{z} + F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z),$$

where m_p is the mass of the nanoparticle; $\gamma = 6\pi\eta a$; η is the dynamic viscosity.

The initial conditions for Eq. (1) are written as:

$$z(0) = z_0, \quad \dot{z}(0) = v_0, \quad (2)$$

where z_0 and v_0 are the initial coordinate and velocity of the nanoparticle.

For small deviations from the initial point z_0 (when $|(z - z_0)\beta| \ll 1$), the exponential can be expanded in a Taylor series in the neighborhood of $z = z_0$ and limited to linear terms:

$$\exp(-\beta z) \approx [1 - (z - z_0)\beta] \exp(-\beta z_0).$$

Then the equation of motion (1) is rewritten as:

$$m_p \ddot{z} = -\gamma \dot{z} + [1 - (z - z_0)\beta] F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0).$$

Rewriting this equation in standard form, grouping terms with z :

$$\begin{aligned} m_p \ddot{z} + \gamma \dot{z} + \beta F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0) z \\ = (1 + \beta z_0) F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The equation (3) is an inhomogeneous linear ordinary differential equation of second order with constant coefficients (for fixed z_0), the solution of which equals the sum of the general solution $z_h(t)$ of the corresponding homogeneous equation

$$m_p \ddot{z} + \gamma \dot{z} + \beta F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0) z = 0 \quad (4)$$

and any particular solution of the inhomogeneous equation (3).

By inspection, the particular solution of Eq. (3) (equilibrium position of the linearized system) is $z_{\text{eq}} = z_0 + 1/\beta$. Thus, the general solution of Eq. (3) has the form $z(t) = z_h(t) + z_0 + 1/\beta$.

For Eq. (3) (or (4)), the characteristic equation has the form:

$$m_p r^2 + \gamma r + \beta F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0) = 0, \quad (5)$$

and its roots

$$r_1 = \frac{-\gamma + \sqrt{D}}{2m_p}, \quad r_2 = \frac{-\gamma - \sqrt{D}}{2m_p},$$

where $D = \gamma^2 - 4m_p\beta F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0)$.

Since $m_p, \gamma, F_0^{\text{scat}}, \beta, \exp(-\beta z_0) > 0$, the real parts of the roots of the characteristic equation (5) are always negative ($\text{Re}(r_{1,2}) < 0$), from which it follows that the equilibrium position $z = 0$ of Eq. (4) (i.e., the equilibrium position $z = z_0 + 1/\beta$ of Eq. (3)) is asymptotically stable.

Depending on the sign of the discriminant D , three cases are possible.

1. Usually, when nanoparticles move in a liquid, friction is large (overdamping), and this case with a large value of the friction force corresponds to the discriminant $D > 0$. The general solution of the homogeneous equation (4) in this case has the form:

$$z_h(t) = A \exp(r_1 t) + B \exp(r_2 t),$$

and the general solution of the inhomogeneous equation (3) has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} z(t) &= z_h(t) + z_0 + 1/\beta \\ &= A \exp(r_1 t) + B \exp(r_2 t) + z_0 + 1/\beta, \end{aligned}$$

where r_1 and r_2 are two distinct real roots of the characteristic equation (5), A and B are integration constants (arbitrary constants), which can be found from the initial conditions (2) as follows:

$$z(0) = A + B + z_0 + 1/\beta = z_0,$$

$$\dot{z}(0) = Ar_1 + Br_2 = v_0.$$

The last leads to

$$A = \frac{v_0 + r_2/\beta}{r_1 - r_2}, \quad B = \frac{-r_1/\beta - v_0}{r_1 - r_2}.$$

Thus, the solution of the Cauchy problem (3)–(2) for the case of overdamping reads:

$$\begin{aligned} z(t) &= z_0 + \frac{1}{\beta} + \frac{m_p}{\sqrt{D}} \left[\left(v_0 + \frac{r_2}{\beta} \right) \exp(r_1 t) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(v_0 + \frac{r_1}{\beta} \right) \exp(r_2 t) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

2. In the case of critical damping, when $D = 0$, the general solution of the homogeneous equation (4) has the form:

$$z_h(t) = (A + Bt) \exp(rt),$$

so that the general solution of the inhomogeneous equation (3) has the form:

$$z(t) = (A + Bt) \exp(rt) + z_0 + 1/\beta,$$

where $r = r_1 = r_2 = -\gamma/(2m_p)$ is a double real root. Using the initial conditions (2) we obtain:

$$z(0) = A + z_0 + 1/\beta = z_0,$$

$$\dot{z}(0) = B + rA = v_0$$

and find the constants $A = -1/\beta$, $B = v_0 - r/\beta$. Thus, the solution of the Cauchy problem (3)–(2) for the case of critical damping is:

$$z(t) = z_0 + \frac{1}{\beta} + \left[\left(v_0 - \frac{r}{\beta} \right) t - \frac{1}{\beta} \right] \exp(rt).$$

3. In the case of underdamping, when $D < 0$, the general solution of the homogeneous equation (4) has the form:

$$z_h(t) = [A \cos(\omega t) + B \sin(\omega t)] \exp(rt),$$

and the general solution of the inhomogeneous equation (3) has the form:

$$z(t) = [A \cos(\omega t) + B \sin(\omega t)] \exp(rt) + z_0 + 1/\beta,$$

where

$$r = \text{Re}(r_{1,2}) = -\frac{\gamma}{2m_p}, \quad \omega = \frac{\sqrt{-D}}{2m_p}.$$

Substitution to the initial conditions (2) we have

$$z(0) = A + z_0 + 1/\beta = z_0,$$

$$\dot{z}(0) = rA + B\omega = v_0$$

so that we find the constants

$$A = -\frac{1}{\beta}, \quad B = \frac{1}{\omega} \left(v_0 + \frac{r}{\beta} \right).$$

Thus, the solution of the Cauchy problem (3)–(2) for the oscillatory case is:

$$z(t) = z_0 + \frac{1}{\beta} + \left[\frac{1}{\omega} \left(v_0 + \frac{r}{\beta} \right) \sin(\omega t) - \frac{1}{\beta} \cos(\omega t) \right] \times \exp(rt).$$

By the substitution $v(t) = \dot{z}(t)$, Eq. (3) is reduced to a system of equations

$$\begin{cases} \dot{z} = v, \\ \dot{v} = \frac{F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0)}{m_p} (1 + \beta z_0 - \beta z) - \frac{\gamma}{m_p} v \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with the phase variables z and v . The singular point (equilibrium point) of this system is the point $(z, v) = (z_0 + 1/\beta, 0)$. In Table 1, the classification of motion regimes for the system (6) depending on the sign of the discriminant D of the characteristic equation is given.

The equation of motion (3) can be brought to the standard form of damped oscillations relative to the equilibrium position z_{eq} :

$$\ddot{z} + 2\delta\dot{z} + \omega_0^2(z_0)(z - z_{\text{eq}}) = 0,$$

where $z_{\text{eq}} = z_0 + 1/\beta$ is the equilibrium position of the linearized system; $\omega_0(z_0) = \sqrt{k_{\text{eff}}(z_0)/m_p}$ is the natural frequency (frequency of small oscillations in the trap in the absence of friction); $k_{\text{eff}}(z_0) = \beta F_0^{\text{scat}} \exp(-\beta z_0)$ is the effective stiffness of the optical trap (or effective elastic coefficient; shows how strongly the light pressure force changes with a small displacement of the particle from the initial point); $\delta = \gamma/(2m_p)$ is the damping coefficient (rate of energy dissipation).

Note that the frequency and effective stiffness depend on the initial position z_0 .

The dimensionless damping coefficient (quality factor):

$$\zeta(z_0) = \frac{\delta}{\omega_0(z_0)} = \frac{\gamma \exp(\beta z_0/2)}{2\sqrt{m_p} \beta F_0^{\text{scat}}}.$$

We write the classification of motion regimes using the parameter ζ :

1. $\zeta > 1$ (same as $D > 0$) – aperiodic regime (overdamping);

Table 1: Type of singular point $(z, v) = (z_0 + 1/\beta, 0)$ of system (6) and corresponding motion regimes.

D	Regime type	Singular point type	Motion character
$D > 0$	Aperiodic	Stable node	Monotonic return to equilibrium without oscillations
$D = 0$	Critical	Degenerate stable node	Boundary case; fastest return to equilibrium without overshoot
$D < 0$	Oscillatory	Stable focus	Damped oscillations around equilibrium position

2. $\zeta = 1$ (same as $D = 0$) — critical regime;
3. $\zeta < 1$ (same as $D < 0$) — oscillatory regime (underdamping).

Capture stability is ensured by the positivity of all coefficients. However, the specific scenario of particle relaxation to the equilibrium position (smoothly or through oscillations) depends on the ratio between the friction force and the effective stiffness of the trap. Since $\zeta(z_0) \propto \exp(\beta z_0/2)$, with increasing initial distance from the surface (z_0), the system tends to the aperiodic regime via the following routes:

1. Near the surface (small z_0), the trap stiffness is large, ω_0 is large, ζ is small; oscillations are possible.
2. Far from the surface (large z_0), the trap stiffness decreases, ω_0 decreases, ζ increases; the motion becomes monotonic (overdamped).

Thus, the sign of the discriminant D and the type of singular point functionally depend on the initial coordinate z_0 .

It is important to note that the linearization used (near the point $z = z_0$) is valid only for small deviations from the initial point, such that $\beta|z(t) - z_0| \ll 1$. This condition must be satisfied throughout the time for which we apply the solution.

In particular, if we consider motion on times much shorter than the relaxation time, then linearization is applicable.

The relaxation time can be estimated as $\tau = 2m_p/\gamma$ for the cases $D = 0$ and $D < 0$, and for $D > 0$ the relaxation time is determined by the root with the smallest absolute value (longest relaxation time).

Thus, for each case we have the following cases:

1. $D > 0$: linearization is applicable for $t \ll \tau$, where $\tau = 1/|r|$, r is the root with the smallest absolute value (slowest decay);
2. $D = 0$: linearization is applicable for $t \ll 2m_p/\gamma$;
3. $D < 0$: linearization is applicable for $t \ll 2m_p/\gamma$ (since damping is determined by the exponential $\exp(-\gamma t/(2m_p))$).

In addition, it is necessary that the initial condition satisfies the condition $\beta|z - z_0| \ll 1$. It is also important to note that the oscillation amplitude in the case $D < 0$ should be small, i.e., the product β times the oscillation amplitude should be much less than unity.

When considering the motion of a nanoparticle under the action of the scattering force of an evanescent wave, the value of β is usually of the order of 10^6 m^{-1} , so that $1/\beta$ equals $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, which is a macroscale for a nanoparticle. For practical applications in the case of nanoparticle motion in the field of an evanescent wave, the initial position z_0 is of the order of nanometers, and $1/\beta$ is of the order of micrometers, so $\beta z_0 \sim 0.001$, which is small, and linearization is applicable. However, over time the particle will move to the equilibrium position

region $z_{\text{eq}} = z_0 + 1/\beta$, where $\beta|z - z_0| \sim 1$, and then linearization ceases to work.

Figures 1–3 show the results of comparison of the numerical solution of the nonlinear equation (1) and the analytical solution of the linearized equation (3) in dimensionless variables $Z = \beta(z - z_0)$, $T = t/\tau$, where $\tau = 2m_p/\gamma$ is the characteristic relaxation time of the system with viscous friction. In Figure 1, the horizontal dashed line $Z = 1$ corresponds to the equilibrium position of the linearized system $z_{\text{eq}} = z_0 + 1/\beta$. In Figures 1 and 2, the vertical dashed lines mark the time moments when the relative error reaches 1%.

Denote by $|Z|_e^\Delta$ the modulus of the difference between the numerical solution of the nonlinear equation (1) and the analytical solution of the linearized equation (3) at the moment when the relative error reaches $e\%$. In Figure 3, the vertical lines show the values of $|Z|_{0.1}^\Delta$ (dotted) and $|Z|_1^\Delta$ (dashed) for each regime. All three curves practically coincide, which confirms the independence of the linearization applicability limit from the sign of the discriminant D .

Analysis shows that the relative error of linearization exceeds 1% at dimensionless displacement $|Z| \approx 0.35\text{--}0.40$ regardless of the sign of the discriminant D of the characteristic equation (5) (Table 2). For a stricter threshold of 0.1%, the corresponding values are $|Z| \approx 0.13\text{--}0.15$.

The spread of values $|Z|_e^\Delta$ for the three motion regimes does not exceed 15%, which indicates a weak dependence of the linearization applicability boundary on the topological type of the singular point of the system phase portrait.

In dimensional units, for a typical value $\beta \approx 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (which corresponds to $1/\beta \approx 1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$), the condition $|Z| \lesssim 0.4$ gives an estimate of the linearization applicability region: $|z - z_0| \lesssim 0.4/\beta \approx 400 \text{ nm}$. For a more accurate description (relative error $< 0.1\%$), this limitation is $|z - z_0| \lesssim 140 \text{ nm}$.

If glass ($n_s = 1.51$) is considered as the dielectric, water ($n_m = 1.33$, $\eta = 0.01 \text{ g}/(\text{cm}\cdot\text{s})$)

FIG. 1. (Color online) The comparison of solutions of nonlinear (solid lines) and linearized (dashed lines) equations of motion (1) and (3) with initial conditions (2) for three regimes: $D > 0$ (blue), $D = 0$ (green), and $D < 0$ (red).

FIG. 2. (Color online) The dependence of the relative error of linearization on dimensionless time for three motion regimes.

as the liquid material, then at the angle of incidence $\theta = 70^\circ$, the case $D > 0$ (aperiodic regime, stable node) is realized for polystyrene ($n_p = 1.59$, $\rho_p = 1.06 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$), polyamide ($n_p = 1.49$, $\rho_p = 1.14 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$), sunflower oil ($n_p = 1.47$, $\rho_p = 0.92 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$), and air bubble ($n_p = 1$, $\rho_p = 1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$) over wide ranges of parameters: $a = 50\text{--}200 \text{ nm}$, $I_0 = 10^2\text{--}10^4 \text{ W}/\text{cm}^2$, $\lambda = 532\text{--}1064 \text{ nm}$.

If rutile ($n_s = 2.6$) is considered as the dielectric, water as the liquid material, then at

Table 2: Applicability bounds of linearization for three regimes of nanoparticle motion.

Regime	D	Singular point type	ζ	$ Z _{1\%}$	$ Z _{0.1\%}$
Aperiodic	0.2761	Stable node	3.10	0.351	0.135
Critical	0.0000	Degenerate node	2.55	0.369	0.139
Oscillatory	-0.8097	Stable focus	1.81	0.400	0.147

FIG. 3. Dependence of the relative error on dimensionless displacement $|Z| = \beta|z - z_0|$ for three motion regimes.

the angle of incidence $\theta = 70^\circ$, the case $D < 0$ (oscillatory regime, stable focus) is realized for TiO_2 ($n_p = 2.49$, $\rho_p = 4.23 \text{ g/cm}^3$), silicon ($n_p = 3.48$, $\rho_p = 2.33 \text{ g/cm}^3$), germanium ($n_p = 4.0$, $\rho_p = 5.32 \text{ g/cm}^3$) at $a = 400 \text{ nm}$, $I_0 = 10^3 -$

10^4 W/cm^2 , $\lambda = 405 \text{ nm}$.

3. Conclusion

An analytical solution for the equation of motion of a nanoparticle under the action of the scattering force of an evanescent wave in the approximation of small displacements is obtained. Numerical modeling has shown that the relative error of the linearized solution exceeds 1% at $\beta|z - z_0| \gtrsim 0.35 - 0.40$ regardless of the sign of the discriminant D of the characteristic equation. Consequently, the applicability region of linearization is determined primarily by dynamic parameters (initial state and process duration), rather than by the topological type of the singular point of the system phase portrait. Linearization is an approximation that can describe the initial stage of motion, when the particle has not yet approached the equilibrium position.

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